

**TOWARDS DEVELOPING SUSTAINABLE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN WITH
LEARNING DISABILITIES IN NIGERIA: A FOCUS ON QUALITY ASSURANCE**

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Abstract

In this paper, developing sustainable inclusive education for children with learning disabilities in Nigeria was discussed. The paper was motivated by the fact that the education of children with learning disabilities within inclusive schools in Nigeria, has hitherto, been unrewarding. Such children in inclusive schools have been observed to be schooling without learning, as the system does not make provisions for addressing their peculiar educational needs; thus, failing to achieve their educational goals. The paper focused on quality assurance's role in effective intervention and service delivery in inclusive education. It also reviewed the concept of learning disabilities and the scope of practice in Nigeria with the extent of inclusive education in Nigeria discussed. The place of quality assurance in educational practice as well as steps towards ensuring quality assurance in inclusive education for learning disabilities intervention was highlighted. It was therefore concluded that the benefit of inclusive education can be achieved within the inclusive school system if quality assurance standards are put in place to check infrastructure, learning methodologies, instructional materials, and competencies of personnel as well as to guide service delivery.

Keywords: Inclusive education; Quality assurance; Learning disabilities.

Introduction

Many countries around the world have identified education as a vehicle for enhancing national development and economic growth. Education, as one of the social institutions, has been a topic of discussion and debate among stakeholders, curriculum bodies, school leaders, policymakers, and implementing agencies. Mba (1995) argues that this was because educational processes did not take into account the individual differences of learners. The reason for this is that children develop differently in terms of physiology and anatomy, thus there are many cases of learning disability among students. Osakwe (2010) argues further, that the school system in Nigeria is now under greater pressure to improve standards, build social and personal competencies, expand curricula, focus more on equal educational opportunities, and prepare students for a fast-changing world. This has implications for the education of children who have learning disabilities, as such children have the potential to play vital roles in national development. Hence, to do so more efficiently and meaningfully, their education must be made a top priority of the government.

The term "inclusive education" describes the idea that children with disabilities should attend general education schools alongside their classmates without disabilities, but with the necessary accommodations and support. Special needs education has moved its emphasis over the last 20 years to inclusive education, which seeks to give all students equal opportunities or backgrounds in learning. The process of making the educational system more capable of reaching a diverse body of children is known as inclusive education. It is predicated on the idea that children with disabilities should be able to participate fully in schooling, provided they receive the support and accommodations they need. Effectiveness, equality of treatment, and equity are the cornerstones of inclusive education, which views diversity as a strength. However, evidence shows that inclusive education is not being adequately implemented in most developing countries.

An estimated 150 million disabled individuals worldwide reside in developing nations, the majority of whom are minors. However, fewer than 2% of these kids are getting any kind of instruction or assistance with their rehabilitation. Accordingly, more individuals with disabilities may receive education and other services in developing nations if inclusive education is successfully implemented (Eleweke & Rodda, 2010). Many instances of disabled children not being able to receive a quality education, participate in society as students, or access education exist in Nigeria. These situations have a significant negative influence on the academic achievement of learning-disabled children. UNICEF reports indicate that the number of Nigerian children not attending school has alarmingly increased (Deji, 2016). The population statistics of Nigeria indicate that there are approximately 20 million children with disabilities in the nation, accounting for 15% of all children in the country.

Children classified as having learning disabilities do not exhibit any overt physical disabilities; instead, they struggle academically in reading, writing, math, and expressive and receptive language. These difficulties are thought to be caused by dysfunction in the central nervous system. They also struggle with information processing, which includes working memory, short-term memory, and metacognitive processes, which include problem-solving abilities, strategy selection, and performance monitoring, among many other academic traits. As a result, they fall into the special needs category in large numbers. According to Martin, Martin, and Carvalho; Lackaye and Margalit as cited in Blume (2010), quality assurance will be required for the education of students with learning disabilities in Nigerian schools as long as ensuring the quality of teaching-learning is prioritized. Quality assurance can help measure, improve, and maintain the high caliber of any human endeavor that has value. It might be in the fields of academia, business, sports, or the financial sector. Olabanji and Abayomi (2013) define quality assurance as the sequence of intentional, systematic actions necessary to provide a high enough level of assurance that a good or service will adhere to quality standards.

The variety of ways that learning disabilities manifest in children across communities, along with the demands that vary depending on the lesson plan, delivery method, resources, environment, evaluation, and intervention techniques at any given moment, make quality assurance in learning disability education essential. To provide children with learning disabilities in Nigeria with a sustainable inclusive education, this paper concentrated on that goal, emphasizing the importance of guaranteeing quality assurance in the services provided to schools. In this paper, quality assurance in educational practice, strategies to ensure quality assurance in learning disabilities intervention in inclusive education, and the concept of learning disabilities and the scope of intervention practice in Nigeria were all covered.

The Concept of Learning Disabilities and the Scope of Intervention Practice in Nigeria

It might be challenging to define learning disabilities as a relatively new category of exceptionality. The complexity of the disorder's presentation and multiple characters have been related to the challenges in defining this area of special needs. Nonetheless, professionals and other stakeholders in the field of learning disorders around the globe are adopting the description provided by the National Joint Committee on Learning Disorders (NJCLD) (1981) in

the United States of America as a broad overview of the nature of learning disabilities. According to the NJCLD, as cited in Bodang (2006), the phrase "learning disabilities" is used to describe a broad range of problems that are characterized by notable challenges in the development and use of speaking, listening, reading, writing, reasoning, and arithmetic skills. These conditions are innate to each person and are thought to result from problems with the central nervous system. Although learning disabilities can coexist with other conditions that make life more difficult, such as mental illness, sensory impairment, social and emotional disturbance, or environmental factors like cultural differences, inadequate instruction, or psychogenic factors, they are not the direct cause of these conditions and influences.

According to the NJCLD criteria, learning disabilities mostly affect children who are able to see and hear and who do not have obvious overall intellectual or physical deficiencies but instead exhibit behavioral and psychological development abnormalities. These are intelligent children, ranging from average to above normal, who struggle with certain academic skills even with excellent instruction. They also have trouble adjusting to life at home and learning through traditional classroom techniques. As a result, individuals need a particular method to achieve their learning objectives.

In Nigeria, not much has been achieved in special needs educational provision for children with learning disabilities in schools. Although these children constitute the largest category of children with special needs and could be found in almost all classes in schools, deliberate efforts have not been made towards attending to their learning needs. The government has not put in place the necessary legislation and quality assurance systems in the area of infrastructural facilities, instructional materials, equipment and gadgets, human resources, and competencies towards enhancing efficacy and full implementation of the programme. The result of these anomalies regarding the education of children with learning disabilities in Nigerian schools is that such children are forced to go through the regular classroom without having their special needs met; hence, do not benefit from teaching-learning experiences (Fuandai, 2010).

Inclusive Education in Nigeria: An Overview

The idea of making education of children and youths with special needs inclusive came to the fore with the Salamanca Declaration in Spain on the future and prospect of special needs education, attended by 92 government delegations and 25 international organizations, towards furthering the objectives of Education For All. According to Ewa (2015), the Salamanca statement argued that inclusive regular schools are the best way to fight discriminatory attitudes, create an inclusive society, and achieve Education for All. These schools can also increase the effectiveness of education for most students and boost the system's overall efficiency and cost-effectiveness. As a result, it suggested and approved the agenda that:

1. every child has a fundamental right to education, and must be given the opportunity to achieve and maintain an acceptable level of learning;
2. every child has unique characteristics, interests, abilities and learning needs;
3. education systems should be designed and educational programmes implemented to take into account the wide diversity of these characteristics and needs; and
4. Those with special educational needs must have access to regular schools that should accommodate them within a child-centered pedagogy capable of meeting these needs.

Inclusive education is a process of enhancing the capacity of the education system in order to reach out to diverse learners. The fundamental goal of inclusion is to guarantee that students with special needs, along with their peers without disabilities who receive general education, benefit from the entire school experience with any necessary

modifications and support (Jonathan & Uchechi, 2017). Thus, children with special needs spend most or all of their time alongside typical students under the inclusive education paradigm, as inclusive education is about the child's right to participate and the school's obligation to accept the child. This is, therefore, different from previously held notions of integration and mainstreaming, which tended to be concerned primarily with disability and special educational needs and implied learners changing or becoming ready for or deserving of accommodation by the mainstream.

According to Patrick and Akinwumi (2015), inclusive education is essentially a policy that the Nigerian government has adopted. Through the Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria has established guidelines for the inclusive education of gifted and talented students as well as children with disabilities who live in disadvantaged environments. Nonetheless, it has been noted that there are issues with the policy's implementation (Ajobiewe, 2004). Like their peers without disabilities, the great majority of Nigerian children with disabilities lack access to high-quality education, social services, and other opportunities because the government has not prioritized the appropriate policies, infrastructure, educational resources, technology, equipment, and human resources to improve the program's effectiveness and full implementation. As a result, it appears that children with learning problems just attend inclusive schools and do not gain anything from the system itself.

Quality Assurance in Educational Practice

Education plans must seek to improve learning outcomes and the quality of education. They must also set concrete goals that governments and other relevant bodies can be held accountable for. Quality assurance refers to continuously achieving product specifications or doing things correctly within a certain procedure. According to Olabanji and Obayomi (2013), citing the National Universities Commission (NUC), quality assurance is a crucial element of successful internationalization, a means of enhancing institutional reputation in the cutthroat local and international marketplace, and a prerequisite for consumer protection. This suggests that to ensure educational outcomes that are in line with global best practices, it is imperative to leverage pertinent inputs and standards. It makes sure that standards are upheld throughout the design and implementation of educational initiatives, ensuring that the final result or product fulfills expectations. According to Olabanji and Obayomi (2013), ensuring quality assurance in the educational enterprise entails identifying and pointing out the elements that are crucial to the assessment of an educational process or other assessable elements; defining the procedures for acting, designating individuals, and preparing the paperwork required for the proper completion of tasks related to a given entity; establishing quality indicators; and routinely analyzing quality with the use of the relevant tools.

The term "quality assurance principles" refers to a way of categorizing and arranging the steps required to guarantee quality; they govern an educational institution's internal and external operations. As a result, it plays a significant role in all facets of school administration and service provision. According to Ozoji (2015), quality assurance works to make sure that high-quality seeds, or inputs, are cultivated in the educational system, or process, to produce high-quality results. That is, quality assurance in education is not a fruit to be reaped at the tail end of a process, but a seed that is sown, built into, and nurtured in the course of all the phases and all facets of education development endeavors, to ensure that the right type of fruits are reaped all along, and in a sustainable manner. Thus, without an adequate quality assurance mechanism, it will be impossible to attain educational aims and objectives to meet the needs of children with learning disabilities in an Inclusive education system.

Towards Ensuring Quality Assurance in Inclusive Education

Ensuring the quality of learning disability interventions can be a difficult undertaking. Comparing it to other physical disabilities, its complexity may account for this. However, the degree of quality control and safeguards implemented during the execution of educational programs will determine how well the Post-2015 Education For All (EFA) and Salamanca aims to turn out. Ozoji (2002) claims that those involved in the education of children

with special needs have not yet given the caliber of education these children receive much thought. Thus, quality assurance safeguards in intervention programs and procedures need to be strengthened if children with learning disabilities are to benefit as much as possible from teaching and learning in accordance with the EFA and Salamanca provisions. This shall be with the aim of ensuring that all children are learning and not just schooling (Obanya in Ozoji, 2015). However, in order to achieve learning disabilities intervention that is consistent with best practices and contemporary demands in Nigeria, there is an urgent need to re-emphasize and reinforce quality assurance mechanisms.

To begin with, it is critical to characterize learning disorders. A lot of nations classify learning disorders based on the features or requirements of their educational framework. The features of the Nigerian educational system are not included in any generic information about learning difficulties in Nigeria. However, learning disabilities are caused by central nervous system dysfunction, according to N.J.C.L.D. 's (1981) definition; the term outlines the issue and traits that suggest the child needs extra care or services. In this situation, a large number of Nigerian children who experience problems at school due to factors like poor instruction or a shortage of resources would not receive therapy. This is made even more apparent by the fact that many children in Nigeria face educational challenges because of the country's educational system, as well as cultural, linguistic, and other obstacles, without the assistance of their teachers. Therefore, a paradigm for learning disabilities needs to be developed that may help children who have learning difficulties because of inadequate or disrupted environments, as well as children with impairments caused by dysfunction of the central nervous system (CNS).

Second, there is a need for differentiated assessment and diagnosis in order to guarantee quality assurance of intervention with respect to learning disabilities. Children categorized as having learning disabilities comprised more than half the students referred for special education services, and many of these children have been misdiagnosed based upon outdated traditional achievement discrepancy model procedures (Fuchs & Fuchs, 2006). Thus, Guthrie as cited in Ihenacho (2007) notes that these assessment practices focused mainly on those abilities that are necessary for the child's learning characteristics against the background of essential potential nutritional and/or metabolic conditions within the child. Hence, it becomes relevant to develop the conditions necessary for determining their learning characteristics as well as nutritional/biochemical status in order to guarantee effective remediation and rehabilitation. Hence, assessment and diagnostic procedures for learning disabilities should be evidence-based.

Thirdly, Contemporary evidence-based remediation and intervention approaches can also guarantee quality services for children with learning disabilities. One of the major problems facing inclusive schools is how to organize specialized intervention programmes for children with learning disabilities. This is due to the heterogeneous manifestation of learning disabilities. Remediation and intervention programmes should therefore be structured in manners that address the physiological, psychological and academic needs of children. This is more so, as learning disabilities are presumed to be intrinsic to the individual, hence, intervention approaches that address academic skills along with physiological and psychological needs are necessary.

Furthermore, to ensure quality assurance in learning disabilities intervention, there is a need for an Individualized Education Programme (IEP) and an Individualized Family Service Plan (IFSP). The Individualized Education Program (IEP) and the Individualized Family Service Plan (IFSP) have similar purposes and function as both provide for communication between parties, written commitment of resources, management of services and a vehicle for monitoring progress. While the Individualized Family Service Plan (IFSP) is a process for planning and documenting the early intervention services required for an infant or toddler (birth to three) with a disability and her/his family, the Individualized Education Program (IEP) is a process for planning and documenting the special education services of school-aged child with a disability from age three through twenty-one years of age. The

Individualized Education Program (IEP) is a programme prepared to meet the individual needs of every child (Andzayi, 2003).

Quality sustainable learning disabilities intervention can also be achieved through strategic transition planning. A planned series of actions that facilitate a student's transition from one educational level to another, from employment to independent living, is known as transition planning. It is determined by the needs, interests, and strengths of individual children. Moving from one grade to the next, through divisions, switching schools or programs, alternating between more specialized programs and the ordinary classroom, and transferring from grade school to postsecondary or employment-related settings are examples of educational transitions. Planning for a transfer effectively starts early, involves the student as much as possible, and is collaborative. Increasing the student's understanding of their own needs and strengths as well as useful coping mechanisms puts them in a better position to make successful and autonomous transitions.

Modifications and accommodations have proven to be essential tactics in the intervention of learning difficulties. To help students with disabilities be successful learners and actively participate in the general education classroom and school-wide activities, accommodations are modifications made to the environment, curriculum, instruction, or assessment procedures. These are adjustments to a student's information access and learning demonstration process; they do not significantly alter the performance standards, instructional level, or content. Rather, they are made to give every student equal access to education and an equal chance to demonstrate their knowledge and abilities. On the other hand, modification describes adjustments to the expectations for what students should learn. The modifications are intended to give a student the chance to engage in classroom and school-related learning experiences in a meaningful and effective way with other students. Changes to the curriculum's instructional level material, performance standards, and assignment structure/pencil work are among the modifications (Statewide Autism Resources & Training Center, 2006).

The educational outcomes of children with learning disabilities have improved due to the employment of information and communication technology (ICT) and assistive technologies. The knowledge and skills of these students have been significantly impacted by the growth of Internet use and Information and Communications Technologies (ICT). In light of the abundance of evidence supporting ICT's usefulness in the instruction of students with special needs, Ozoji (2015) asserts that there is no questioning the benefits of ICT for special needs education. The use of assistive technology can increase self-reliance and independence, improve chances of success in education, the workplace, and life, as well as help children with learning disabilities complete tasks that they were previously unable to complete or found extremely difficult. It can also enhance or modify existing methods of interacting with the technology needed to accomplish such tasks.

It is impossible to overstate the importance of teacher competencies in ensuring quality assurance in learning disability interventions. Instructors working with students who have learning difficulties must possess exceptional technical proficiency in all areas of the programs they teach. These teachers should possess technical competencies in the areas of learning disability theories, curriculum and teaching material knowledge, assessment and evaluation skills, behavior management, social and emotional intelligence, pre-vocational and vocational skills, grammar and reading instruction, and assessment and evaluation (Houch, 1984). They should also be proficient in a variety of tests.

Because learning disabilities can present in a variety of ways, interdisciplinary collaboration is necessary to build multi-disciplinary support through a variety of specialized services, organizations, and resource centers. This kind of collaboration is essential to providing a comprehensive and seamless service to support children with learning disabilities. This is especially true given that different disciplines and professions have differing views on what exactly qualifies as a learning disability. These include education, psychology, neurology, neuropsychology,

optometry, psychiatry, and speech and language pathology, to name a few. Each of these disciplines has traditionally focused on different aspects of the child or adult with a learning disability, so divergent ideas and contentious disagreements exist about the importance of etiology, diagnostic methods, intervention methods, and professional roles and responsibilities.

In Nigeria, the current condition of the inclusive education system primarily serves the needs of students with evident special education requirements. As a result, students with learning difficulties may attend school but not benefit from the educational gains that the inclusive system is supposed to provide. Even though they confront many obstacles in the classroom and make up the majority of children with special needs, children with learning difficulties have potential that can be nurtured and utilized to help them meet their academic objectives. If quality assurance standards are implemented to direct and improve infrastructure and equipment, teaching-learning methodologies and instructional materials, personnel competencies, and service, then these children can benefit from inclusive education within the inclusive school system.

Recommendations

1. Special needs professionals in the area of learning disabilities need to come together and come up with a definition of learning disabilities that is encompassing and will address the myriad of learning problems that emanate both from intrinsic factors and from environmental factors.
2. Accommodation, modification and strategic transition planning should be a core requirement for the requirement in inclusive schools to ensure children with learning disabilities are learning and not just schooling.
3. Standard criteria for diagnosis, identification, and remediation of learning disabilities should be fashioned out in order to guarantee the quality of intervention programmes.
4. Quality assurance procedures in the aspects of infrastructure, teaching methodologies, instructional materials and teacher competencies should be clearly spelled out for effective service delivery in inclusive education.
5. Multi-disciplinary team support through a range of different specialist services, organizations, and resource centers, working collaboratively to provide a comprehensive and seamless service to support children with learning disabilities is very crucial.
6. Evidence-based intervention should integrate both classroom remedial activities and micro-nutrient intervention in order to address both the intrinsic factors of learning disabilities and the obvious learning characteristics.

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